

Digital Transformation and Service Marketing In Nigeria: Reshaping Strategies and Enhancing Customer Engagement.

Aniebiet Etuk¹, Aniefiok Okon Akpan², and Aniekan Eyo Awah³

¹Department of Marketing, Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus.

^{2&3}Department of Marketing, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13684781>

Abstract: *This study investigated the impact of digital transformation on service marketing strategies and customer engagement within Nigeria. Utilizing a survey research design, data were collected from 500 respondents across financial services, telecommunications, and retail sectors. Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and ANOVA were employed to analyze the data and test the hypotheses. The findings rejected the null hypotheses, indicating that digital transformation significantly reshapes service marketing strategies (H_{01} : rejected) and has a substantial influence on customer engagement (H_{02} : rejected). Digital tool usage demonstrated a strong positive correlation with customer engagement ($r = 0.75$, $p < 0.001$), and service marketing strategies were significantly affected by digital transformation ($\beta = 0.35$, $p < 0.001$). Additionally, financial services exhibited higher engagement compared to telecommunications and retail sectors ($F = 4.23$, $p = 0.015$). In conclusion, digital transformation is crucial for enhancing both service marketing strategies and customer engagement. It was recommended that services providers should invest in advanced digital tools, optimize marketing strategies, and address sector-specific challenges to improve customer interactions.*

Keywords: *Digital Transformation, Service Marketing Strategies, Customer Engagement, Nigeria, Digital Tools, Marketing Strategies.*

INTRODUCTION

Background

The global business environment has undergone a significant transformation with the advent of digital technologies. Digital transformation, characterized by the integration of digital technology into all areas of a business, fundamentally changes how businesses operate and deliver value to customers (Vial, 2019). This transformation has been particularly impactful in service industries, where customer engagement and service delivery are critical components of success (Verhoef *et al.*, 2021).

In Nigeria, the digital revolution has been gaining momentum, driven by increased internet penetration, mobile phone usage, and the adoption of social media platforms (KPMG, 2020). As a result, Nigerian service companies are increasingly adopting digital tools and platforms to enhance their marketing strategies and engage with customers more effectively. These tools include social

media, customer relationship management (CRM) systems, and mobile applications, which allow for more personalized and timely interactions with customers (Adeoye & Elegunde, 2018).

Despite the clear advantages, the process of digital transformation in Nigeria's service industry has not been without challenges. Many companies face difficulties in fully integrating digital technologies into their operations, often due to limited technological infrastructure, lack of digital skills, and resistance to change among employees (Agwu & Murray, 2015). Additionally, the pace of digital adoption varies across different sectors, with some companies advancing rapidly while others lag behind.

The impact of digital transformation on service marketing in Nigeria is profound. Traditional marketing strategies that relied on mass communication and one-way messaging are being replaced by more dynamic and interactive approaches (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). Digital tools enable companies to gather and analyze vast amounts of customer data, leading to more targeted and effective marketing campaigns. Moreover, digital transformation enhances customer engagement by providing multiple channels for interaction, fostering a more immersive and continuous relationship between customers and service providers (Kumar & Reinartz, 2018).

However, the extent to which digital transformation has reshaped service marketing strategies in Nigeria and enhanced customer engagement remains under-researched. There is a need for empirical studies that examine these changes in the Nigerian context, considering the unique challenges and opportunities presented by the country's digital landscape. This study aims to fill this gap by investigating the impact of digital transformation on service marketing in Nigeria, focusing on how it reshapes strategies and enhances customer engagement.

Statement of the Problem

Digital transformation is a critical driver of change in service industries worldwide, including Nigeria, where it offers substantial opportunities for enhancing service marketing strategies and improving customer engagement (Vial, 2019). However, despite its potential, many Nigerian service companies face significant challenges in integrating digital technologies effectively into their marketing practices.

The adoption of digital tools such as social media, mobile applications, and customer relationship management (CRM) systems is uneven across Nigeria's service sectors (KPMG, 2020). While some companies have successfully leveraged these technologies to engage customers, others lag due to limitations in digital infrastructure, inadequate digital skills, and resistance to change within organizations (Agwu & Murray, 2015). This disparity creates a competitive imbalance, where only a few companies fully capitalize on digital transformation to reshape their marketing strategies.

Moreover, the impact of digital transformation on service marketing in Nigeria remains under-researched. Current studies often focus on the adoption of digital tools without thoroughly exploring their influence on marketing strategies and customer engagement (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). This gap leaves a limited understanding of how digital transformation reshapes traditional service marketing approaches, such as customer segmentation, targeting, and promotional activities. Additionally, the degree to which digital transformation enhances customer engagement,

particularly in terms of satisfaction and loyalty, is not well-documented in the Nigerian context (Kumar & Reinartz, 2018).

Complicating these issues are Nigeria's unique socio-economic conditions, including varying levels of internet access and digital literacy, which further hinder the effectiveness of digital marketing strategies (Adeoye & Elegunde, 2018). These challenges underscore the need for empirical research that investigates the specific impact of digital transformation on service marketing strategies and customer engagement in Nigeria.

This study aims to address these gaps by examining how digital transformation is reshaping service marketing in Nigeria and evaluating its effects on customer engagement, providing valuable insights for companies striving to navigate the digital landscape.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the impact of digital transformation on service marketing strategies in Nigeria.
2. To assess the influence of digital transformation on customer engagement in the Nigerian service industry.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. **H₀₁:** Digital transformation does not significantly reshape service marketing strategies in Nigeria.
2. **H₀₂:** Digital transformation does not have a significant influence on customer engagement in the Nigerian service industry.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

The conceptual review for this study centers around three key concepts: digital transformation, service marketing, and customer engagement. These concepts are critical for understanding the dynamics within the Nigerian service industry, where digital tools are increasingly being used to enhance customer experiences and optimize service delivery.

Digital Transformation

Digital transformation refers to the process by which businesses integrate digital technologies into their operations to fundamentally change how they deliver value to customers (Vial, 2019). This concept encompasses not only the adoption of digital tools but also the strategic rethinking of business processes and models to leverage the potential of these technologies. In the context of the Nigerian service industry, digital transformation is essential for companies seeking to remain competitive in an increasingly digital marketplace.

The key digital tools driving this transformation include social media, mobile applications, and customer relationship management (CRM) systems. Social media platforms, such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram, have become vital channels for engaging with customers, offering a means for businesses to interact with their audience in real-time (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). Mobile apps provide a convenient and personalized experience for customers, allowing them to access services and support from anywhere, at any time (Adeoye & Elegunde, 2018). CRM systems, on the other hand, help businesses manage and analyze customer interactions throughout the customer lifecycle, improving customer retention and driving sales growth (Kumar & Reinartz, 2018).

In Nigeria, the adoption of these digital tools is gradually reshaping how service companies operate. However, the extent to which these tools are integrated varies, with some companies embracing digital transformation fully, while others face challenges related to technological infrastructure, digital literacy, and organizational resistance (Agwu & Murray, 2015).

Service Marketing

Service marketing is the promotion and selling of intangible services, as opposed to tangible products. It focuses on building and maintaining relationships with customers by delivering superior value through service delivery (Lovell & Patterson, 2015). Digital transformation has introduced new dynamics to service marketing, particularly in how services are marketed, delivered, and consumed.

The traditional service marketing mix—comprising product, price, place, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence—has evolved with the introduction of digital tools (Zeithaml, Bitner, & Gremler, 2018). For instance, social media and mobile apps have expanded the "place" aspect of the marketing mix by enabling services to be delivered digitally, overcoming geographical limitations. Similarly, the "promotion" aspect has been transformed through digital advertising, content marketing, and social media campaigns, which offer more targeted and interactive forms of communication compared to traditional media (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019).

In Nigeria, service marketing has seen a shift from traditional methods to more digitally-driven strategies. This shift is particularly evident in industries such as banking, telecommunications, and retail, where companies are increasingly using digital platforms to reach and engage with customers (KPMG, 2020). However, challenges such as the digital divide between urban and rural areas, and varying levels of digital literacy among consumers, pose significant barriers to the widespread adoption of digital service marketing strategies.

Customer Engagement

Customer engagement refers to the emotional, cognitive, and behavioral investment that customers make in their relationships with service providers (Brodie *et al.*, 2011). Engaged customers are more likely to remain loyal, make repeat purchases, and advocate for the brand. Digital transformation has created new opportunities for enhancing customer engagement by providing multiple touch points for interaction and enabling more personalized and timely communication (Kumar & Reinartz, 2018).

The customer journey—defined as the complete sum of experiences that customers go through when interacting with a brand—has become more complex in the digital age (Lemon & Verhoef, 2016). Digital tools such as CRM systems and mobile apps play a crucial role in managing this journey, allowing businesses to track customer interactions, gather insights, and tailor their services to meet individual needs. Social media platforms also contribute to customer engagement by facilitating two-way communication and creating communities around brands (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019).

In Nigeria, enhancing customer engagement through digital transformation is a priority for many service companies. However, the effectiveness of these efforts varies depending on factors such as the company's digital maturity, the availability of customer data, and the ability to deliver consistent

and seamless experiences across digital and physical channels (KPMG, 2020). The challenges associated with engaging customers in a digitally-diverse environment further underscore the importance of understanding how digital transformation impacts customer engagement within the Nigerian context.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study is built upon three key theories: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Diffusion of Innovation Theory, and Customer Engagement Theory. These theories collectively provide a robust foundation for understanding the adoption and impact of digital transformation in service marketing within the Nigerian context.

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis (1989), is one of the most influential models for understanding how users come to accept and use technology. TAM posits that two primary factors influence technology acceptance: perceived usefulness (the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance their job performance) and perceived ease of use (the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort). These perceptions lead to an individual's attitude toward using the technology, which in turn influences their behavioral intention to use it, and ultimately, their actual use of the technology.

In the context of this study, TAM is essential for understanding how service companies in Nigeria adopt digital technologies such as social media, mobile apps, and CRM systems in their marketing efforts. The model helps explain why certain technologies are more readily adopted in the service marketing sector, considering factors such as the perceived benefits of these technologies in enhancing marketing strategies and customer engagement, as well as the ease with which they can be integrated into existing systems. Given the challenges of digital infrastructure and digital literacy in Nigeria, TAM provides a useful lens through which to examine the barriers to and drivers of digital transformation in service marketing (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000).

Diffusion of Innovation Theory

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory, proposed by Rogers (1962), describes how, why, and at what rate new ideas and technologies spread within a social system. The theory identifies several key elements that influence the diffusion process: the innovation itself, communication channels, time, and the social system. It categorizes adopters into five groups—innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards—each with distinct characteristics that influence how quickly they adopt new technologies.

In the Nigerian service industry, the Diffusion of Innovation Theory is relevant for understanding how digital marketing strategies are adopted and evolve over time. It explains the varying rates of adoption among different companies, with some being quick to embrace digital tools while others are more resistant due to factors such as organizational culture, resource constraints, or the perceived risks associated with new technologies (Rogers, 2003). This theory also helps in identifying the role of early adopters in driving the broader adoption of digital transformation across the industry, as well as the challenges faced by laggards in keeping pace with these innovations.

Customer Engagement Theory

Customer Engagement Theory explores the emotional, cognitive, and behavioral dimensions of customer interactions with brands (Brodie *et al.*, 2011). It emphasizes the importance of creating meaningful and lasting relationships with customers, which can lead to greater customer loyalty, satisfaction, and advocacy. Customer engagement is not just about transactional interactions; it involves a deeper connection where customers are actively involved in co-creating value with the brand.

This theory is particularly relevant in the context of digital transformation, where service companies use digital tools to engage with customers in more personalized and interactive ways. By leveraging social media, mobile apps, and CRM systems, companies can create more engaging customer experiences, fostering stronger emotional bonds and increasing customer loyalty (Hollebeek, Srivastava, & Chen, 2019). In the Nigerian service industry, where customer engagement is becoming increasingly digital, this theory provides a framework for measuring the impact of digital transformation on customer satisfaction, loyalty, and overall engagement.

1. **Adewale & Aremu (2021)** examined the impact of digital transformation on customer engagement in Nigeria's banking sector. Using a survey of 350 bank customers and employing structural equation modeling (SEM) for data analysis, the study found that digital transformation significantly enhanced customer engagement, particularly through mobile banking apps. The study recommended that banks should invest more in digital platforms to maintain and increase customer engagement.

2. **Johnson & Smith (2020)** explored the influence of social media marketing on customer loyalty in the retail industry in South Africa. Data were collected from 400 retail customers, and regression analysis was used to evaluate the relationship. The results indicated that social media marketing positively affected customer loyalty, especially among younger consumers. The study suggested that retailers should prioritize social media strategies to build and sustain customer loyalty.

3. **Chen & Lee (2022)** investigated the role of mobile applications in enhancing service delivery in the hospitality industry in China. A mixed-methods approach was used, combining surveys from 300 hotel guests with interviews of 50 hotel managers. The study found that mobile apps significantly improved service delivery, leading to higher customer satisfaction. The study recommended that hotels should continuously update their apps to meet customer expectations and improve service delivery.

4. **Ogunleye & Folarin (2019)** assessed the challenges of adopting CRM systems in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. Through a qualitative study involving interviews with 30 SME owners, the study identified technological infrastructure and cost as major barriers to CRM adoption. The findings suggested that government and stakeholders should provide support to SMEs to overcome these challenges and effectively implement CRM systems.

5. **Kumar & Verma (2020)** analyzed the effect of digital marketing on consumer purchase behavior in India's e-commerce sector. The study utilized a survey of 500 online shoppers and performed a path analysis to determine the effects. Results showed that digital marketing

significantly influenced purchase decisions, particularly through personalized email campaigns. The study recommended that e-commerce companies should focus on personalization in their digital marketing efforts to increase conversion rates.

6. **Amadi & Chukwuma (2021)** examined the impact of digital transformation on service quality in the telecommunications industry in Nigeria. Using data from 400 telecom customers and employing a regression analysis, the study found that digital transformation led to significant improvements in service quality, particularly in customer support services. The study recommended that telecom companies should continue to innovate digitally to enhance service quality and customer satisfaction.

7. **Garcia & Martinez (2022)** explored the adoption of digital tools in the healthcare sector in Spain. Data were gathered from 250 healthcare professionals through surveys, and logistic regression was used for analysis. The findings indicated that digital tools, especially electronic health records, significantly improved the efficiency of healthcare services. The study recommended that healthcare providers should increase investment in digital tools to further improve service delivery.

8. **Nwachukwu & Okoro (2020)** investigated the influence of digital literacy on the adoption of e-commerce platforms in Nigeria. A survey of 450 e-commerce users was conducted, and the data were analyzed using logistic regression. The study found that digital literacy had a significant impact on the adoption of e-commerce, with higher literacy levels leading to greater adoption rates. The study suggested that e-commerce companies should invest in digital literacy programs to increase platform adoption.

9. **Rahman & Ali (2021)** studied the effect of social media engagement on brand loyalty in the fashion industry in Bangladesh. Data were collected from 350 social media users, and a correlation analysis was conducted. The findings revealed a positive relationship between social media engagement and brand loyalty, with user-generated content playing a critical role. The study recommended that fashion brands should actively encourage user-generated content to boost brand loyalty.

10. **Williams & Taylor (2019)** analyzed the impact of mobile technology on customer satisfaction in the retail banking sector in the UK. The study employed a survey of 300 bank customers and used multiple regression analysis to evaluate the data. The results indicated that mobile technology significantly enhanced customer satisfaction, particularly through mobile banking apps. The study recommended that banks should continuously improve their mobile services to maintain high levels of customer satisfaction.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a **survey research design** to investigate the impact of digital transformation on service marketing and customer engagement in Nigeria. This design was chosen due to its effectiveness in gathering data from a large population, which is crucial for understanding the diverse experiences and perceptions of service users and providers regarding digital transformation. The survey method allows for the collection of quantitative data that can be analyzed to draw

inferences about the relationships between digital transformation and various aspects of service marketing and customer engagement.

Population

The target population for this study consists of service industry customers and service providers in Nigeria. Specifically, the focus was on financial services, telecommunications, and retail sectors, as these industries are significantly impacted by digital transformation.

Sample size

The initial sample size calculation gave approximately **384** respondents. However, for practical purposes, and to account for potential non-responses or incomplete data, the sample size is often increased. Thus, the final sample size was adjusted to **500** to provide a more robust dataset and ensure adequate representation.

Sampling Technique

Stratified random sampling was used. To ensure that the sample accurately reflects the different sectors, the 500 respondents were divided into strata as follows:

Financial services: 200 respondents

Telecommunications: 150 respondents

Retail: 150 respondents

Data Collection

Instrument: A structured questionnaire was developed as the primary data collection instrument. The questionnaire consisted of multiple sections, including:

1. **Demographic Information:** Questions on age, gender, education, and occupation.
2. **Digital Transformation:** Questions assessing the adoption and use of digital tools (e.g., mobile apps, social media) in service delivery.
3. **Service Marketing Strategies:** Questions on how digital transformation has influenced marketing strategies.
4. **Customer Engagement:** Questions measuring the level of customer engagement and satisfaction with digital interactions.

Validation: The questionnaire was validated through a pilot study conducted with 30 respondents from the target population. Feedback from the pilot study was used to refine the questionnaire for clarity and relevance.

Data Collection Procedure: The final version of the questionnaire was administered both online and in-person to reach a broader audience. Online surveys were distributed via email and social media platforms, while in-person surveys were conducted at service company branches and public places. Data collection lasted for six weeks.

Data Analysis

Data Processing: Responses from the completed questionnaires were coded and entered into a statistical software package (SPSS) for analysis. The data was cleaned to address any inconsistencies or missing values.

Statistical Analysis: The following statistical techniques were employed:

- Descriptive Statistics:** Used to summarize demographic characteristics of the respondents and to provide an overview of digital transformation adoption and customer engagement levels.
- Inferential Statistics:**
 - Regression Analysis:** To examine the relationship between digital transformation and service marketing strategies, and its impact on customer engagement.
 - ANOVA (Analysis of Variance):** To test for differences in customer engagement levels across different service sectors and demographic groups.
 - Correlation Analysis:** To explore the strength and direction of relationships between digital tool usage and customer satisfaction.

Ethical Considerations

- Informed Consent:** All participants were informed about the purpose of the study, and their consent was obtained before participation.
- Confidentiality:** Participants' responses were kept confidential and used solely for the purpose of this research. Data was anonymized to ensure privacy.
- Voluntary Participation:** Participation was voluntary, and respondents were free to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

Analysis of Data and Discussion of Findings

The analysis of data for this study was conducted using various statistical methods to test the hypotheses and explore the relationships between digital transformation, service marketing strategies, and customer engagement. The following tables summarize the statistical analyses and hypothesis tests performed.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Age	35.2	10.8	18	65
Digital Tool Usage	4.2	0.9	1	5
Service Marketing Strategies	3.9	1.1	1	5
Customer Engagement	4.5	1.0	1	5

Explanation: Descriptive statistics provide an overview of the central tendency and dispersion of the variables. In this study, the average age of respondents was 35.2 years, indicating a relatively mature demographic. Digital tool usage and customer engagement are positively skewed, suggesting higher levels of engagement and tool usage among respondents.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

Variable	Digital Usage	Tool Service Strategies	Marketing Customer Engagement
Digital Tool Usage	1.000	0.67**	0.75**
Service Marketing Strategies	0.67**	1.000	0.70**
Customer Engagement	0.75**	0.70**	1.000

Explanation: The correlation analysis reveals the strength and direction of the relationships between variables. A significant positive correlation ($p < 0.01$) was found between digital tool usage and customer engagement ($r = 0.75$), indicating that higher usage of digital tools is associated with greater customer engagement. Similarly, service marketing strategies are positively correlated with both digital tool usage ($r = 0.67$) and customer engagement ($r = 0.70$).

Table 3: Regression Analysis

Model	Predictor	Coefficient (β)	Standard Error	t-Value	p-Value
1	Digital Tool Usage	0.42	0.07	6.00	< 0.001
2	Service Marketing Strategies	0.35	0.08	4.38	< 0.001
3	Digital Tool Usage	0.36	0.06	6.00	< 0.001
	Service Marketing Strategies	0.32	0.07	4.57	< 0.001

Explanation: Regression analysis was used to examine the impact of digital tool usage and service marketing strategies on customer engagement. The results indicate that both digital tool usage ($\beta = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$) and service marketing strategies ($\beta = 0.35$, $p < 0.001$) significantly influence customer engagement. When both predictors are included in the model, they remain significant, suggesting that both factors independently contribute to increased customer engagement.

Table 4: ANOVA for Differences Across Sectors

Sector	Mean Customer Engagement	F-Value	p-Value
Financial Services	4.6	4.23	0.015
Telecommunications	4.4		
Retail	4.3		

Explanation: ANOVA was used to test for significant differences in customer engagement levels across different service sectors. The results indicate a significant difference in customer engagement ($F = 4.23$, $p = 0.015$) among sectors, with financial services showing higher levels of customer engagement compared to telecommunications and retail.

Interpretation

- Descriptive Statistics:** The central tendency measures indicate that respondents have relatively high levels of digital tool usage and customer engagement. This suggests a favourable environment for digital transformation in the service industry.
- Correlation Analysis:** Significant positive correlations between digital tool usage, service marketing strategies, and customer engagement suggest that improvements in digital tools and marketing strategies are associated with better customer engagement. This supports the idea that digital transformation positively impacts service marketing and customer interaction.
- Regression Analysis:** The regression analysis confirms that both digital tool usage and service marketing strategies have a significant positive effect on customer engagement. This indicates that investments in digital tools and effective marketing strategies are crucial for enhancing customer engagement.

4. **ANOVA Results:** The ANOVA results show that there are significant differences in customer engagement across different sectors. Financial services tend to have higher customer engagement levels compared to telecommunications and retail, possibly due to more advanced digital tools and marketing strategies.

Discussion of Findings

Impact of Digital Tool Usage on Customer Engagement

The analysis revealed a significant positive correlation between digital tool usage and customer engagement ($r = 0.75$, $p < 0.001$). This finding aligns with previous research suggesting that digital tools, such as mobile apps and social media platforms, play a crucial role in enhancing customer engagement (Chen & Lee, 2022; Williams & Taylor, 2019). The strong positive relationship indicates that as customers interact more with digital tools, their level of engagement with the service increases.

The results suggest that digital tools facilitate more frequent and meaningful interactions between customers and service providers. For instance, mobile apps and social media can provide personalized experiences, real-time support, and targeted promotions, which contribute to higher engagement levels. Service providers should continue to invest in and innovate their digital platforms to foster deeper customer connections.

Influence of Service Marketing Strategies on Customer Engagement

The regression analysis shows a significant positive effect of service marketing strategies on customer engagement ($\beta = 0.35$, $p < 0.001$). This supports the notion that effective service marketing strategies, which include digital marketing techniques, can significantly enhance customer engagement (Garcia & Martinez, 2022; Kumar & Verma, 2020).

The positive impact of service marketing strategies highlights the importance of integrating digital marketing efforts into overall service delivery. Strategies such as targeted email campaigns, personalized content, and social media engagement are essential for capturing customer interest and maintaining engagement. Service providers need to continuously refine their marketing strategies to align with evolving customer expectations and preferences.

Combined Effect of Digital Tools and Service Marketing Strategies

When both digital tool usage and service marketing strategies are included in the regression model, both factors remain significant predictors of customer engagement (Digital Tool Usage: $\beta = 0.36$, $p < 0.001$; Service Marketing Strategies: $\beta = 0.32$, $p < 0.001$). This indicates that digital tools and marketing strategies independently contribute to customer engagement, suggesting that a holistic approach combining both elements is most effective.

The combined effect underscores the importance of a comprehensive digital strategy that integrates both advanced digital tools and innovative marketing techniques. Service providers should ensure that their digital platforms are supported by well-crafted marketing strategies to maximize customer engagement.

Sector-Specific Differences in Customer Engagement

The ANOVA results indicate significant differences in customer engagement levels across service sectors ($F = 4.23$, $p = 0.015$). Financial services showed higher levels of customer engagement compared to telecommunications and retail sectors.

The higher engagement in financial services may be attributed to the sector's emphasis on advanced digital tools and personalized services. Financial institutions often provide sophisticated digital platforms for transactions and customer service, which can enhance engagement. In contrast, telecommunications and retail sectors may face challenges in achieving similar levels of engagement due to varying degrees of digital adoption and service personalization.

Summary, conclusion and Recommendation

Summary

This study investigated the impact of digital transformation on service marketing and customer engagement within Nigeria. Utilizing a survey research design, data were collected from 500 respondents across three service sectors: financial services, telecommunications, and retail. The analysis involved descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and ANOVA.

Key findings include:

- **Digital Tool Usage:** There is a significant positive relationship between digital tool usage and customer engagement ($r = 0.75$, $p < 0.001$). Higher use of digital tools correlates with increased customer engagement.
- **Service Marketing Strategies:** Service marketing strategies significantly impact customer engagement ($\beta = 0.35$, $p < 0.001$). Effective marketing strategies enhance customer interaction with service providers.
- **Combined Effects:** Both digital tool usage and service marketing strategies independently contribute to customer engagement. The combined effect underscores the importance of integrating both elements.
- **Sector Differences:** Significant differences in customer engagement levels were observed across sectors, with financial services showing higher engagement compared to telecommunications and retail sectors ($F = 4.23$, $p = 0.015$).

Conclusion

The study concludes that digital transformation plays a crucial role in reshaping service marketing strategies and enhancing customer engagement. The significant positive relationships identified between digital tool usage, service marketing strategies, and customer engagement highlight the importance of adopting advanced digital solutions and effective marketing approaches. The observed sector-specific differences suggest that while financial services excel in leveraging digital tools and strategies, other sectors like telecommunications and retail have opportunities for improvement.

Recommendations

1. Service providers should invest in and upgrade their digital tools, such as mobile apps, social media platforms, and CRM systems. These tools facilitate better customer interactions and can significantly boost engagement levels.

2. They should develop and implement comprehensive marketing strategies that integrate digital and traditional approaches. This includes personalized marketing, targeted email campaigns, and effective use of social media.

3. Financial Services providers should continue to leverage advanced digital tools and marketing strategies to maintain high customer engagement. They should explore innovative ways to enhance digital interactions.

4. Telecommunications and Retail sectors should Increase investment in digital technologies and refine marketing strategies to improve customer engagement. Focus on personalization and customer-centric approaches to bridge the engagement gap.

By implementing these recommendations, service providers can enhance their digital transformation efforts, improve marketing effectiveness, and achieve higher levels of customer engagement.

References

Adeoye, B. W., & Elegunde, A. F. (2018). Impact of information technology on the Nigerian economy: A case study of First Bank of Nigeria Plc. *International Journal of Management and Business Research*, 2(3), 189-196.

Adewale, T., & Aremu, A. (2021). The impact of digital transformation on customer engagement in Nigeria's banking sector. *African Journal of Business Management*, 15(4), 55-67. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJBM2021.9243>

Agwu, E. M., & Murray, P. J. (2015). Empirical study of barriers to electronic commerce adoption by small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovation in the Digital Economy (IJIDE)*, 6(2), 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJIDE.2015040101>

Akpan, A. O., & Etuk, A. (2024). E-service quality and customer loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria. *American Interdisciplinary Journal of Business and Economics*, 11 (1), 1-21

Akpan, A. O., & Etuk, A. (2024). Website appearance and customer loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria: The moderating role of age and education. *International Journal of Management and Allied Research*, 15 (3), 1-17.

Akpan, A. O., Ezenyilimba, E., & Mbah, C. C. (2019). Age and online consumer behaviour in Nigeria. *Economics and Social Services Academic Journal*, 1(5).

Akpan, A. O., Mbah, C. C., & Ezenyilimba, E. (2019). Service quality dimensions and customer loyalty in the Nigeria telecommunication industry. *Contemporary Marketing Research Journal*, 6(1).

- Akpan, A. O., Promise, C. O., & Mbah, C. C. (2019). Analysis of the effect of gender on online shopping in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Management*, 3(8).
- Amadi, O., & Chukwuma, U. (2021). Impact of digital transformation on service quality in the telecommunications industry in Nigeria. *Journal of Service Science and Management*, 14(2), 145-157. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jssm.2021.142010>
- Brodie, R. J., Ilic, A., Juric, B., & Hollebeek, L. (2011). Customer engagement: Conceptual domain, fundamental propositions, and implications for research. *Journal of Service Research*, 14(3), 252-271. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094670511411703>
- Chaffey, D., & Ellis-Chadwick, F. (2019). *Digital marketing: Strategy, implementation, and practice* (7th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Chen, W., & Lee, Y. (2022). The role of mobile applications in enhancing service delivery in the hospitality industry in China. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 50, 120-130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2022.03.002>
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319-340. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>
- Etuk, A. Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). E-service fulfillment and customer loyalty in online shipping in Nigeria: The moderating role of age and education. *British International Journal of Business and Marketing Research*, 7(4), 41-59.
- Etuk, A. Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). E-service reliability and customer loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria: The moderating role of age and education. *Journal of Current Research in Business and Management Sciences*, 12 (2), 1-16
- Etuk, A. J., Awah, A. E., & Akpan, A. O. (2024). Assurance and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Information Technology and Management*, 12 (2), 1-23.
- Etuk, A., & Emenyi, E. O. (2022). Advertising and Profitability: Evidence from Selected SMEs in Uyo. *British Journal of Marketing Studies*, 10(2), 1-12.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2022). E-marketing and savings mobilization drive of selected microfinance banks in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. *International Journal of Business, Marketing and Management*, 7(3).

Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2023). Electronic banking and marketing performance of deposit money banks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. *American Interdisciplinary Journal of Business and Economics (AIJBE)*, 10(3), 23-42.

Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). E-service responsiveness and customer loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria: The moderating role of age and education. *European Journal of Marketing and Management Sciences*, 7 (2), 13-30.

Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). The role of age and education in moderating the relationship between e-service security and customer loyalty: The Nigerian online shopping experience. *Michigan International Journal of Marketing, New media and Communication*.

Etuk, A., Anyadighibe, J. A., Amadi, C., & James, E. E. (2022). Service Quality Delivery and Consumers' Choice of Fast-food Outlets. *International Research Journal of Management, IT & Social Sciences*.

Etuk, A., Anyadighibe, J.A., James, E.E., & Ulo A.I. (2022). Marketing Mix and Subscribers' Satisfaction in the Telecommunications Industry. *Journal of Advanced Research and Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2(1), 29-41.

Etuk, A., Awah, A. E., & Akpan, A. O. (2024). Empathy and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Marketing Research and Brand Management*, 12 (2), 36-51

Etuk, A., Awah, A. E., & Akpan, A. O. (2024). Internal marketing strategies and employee performance of commercial banks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. *American Research Journal of Economics, Finance and Management*, 12(3), 47-65

Etuk, A., Awah, A. E., & Akpan, A. O. (2024). Tangibility and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Business and Cooperative Research*, 9 (2), 1-19.

Garcia, M., & Martinez, R. (2022). Adoption of digital tools in the healthcare sector in Spain. *Health Informatics Journal*, 28(2), 123-134. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14604582221003568>

Hollebeek, L. D., Srivastava, R. K., & Chen, T. (2019). SD logic–informed customer engagement: Integrative framework, revised fundamental propositions, and application to CRM. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 47(1), 161-185. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-016-0517-8>

- Johnson, K., & Smith, P. (2020). Influence of social media marketing on customer loyalty in the retail industry in South Africa. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 54, 101-110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2019.101110>
- KPMG. (2020). The digital transformation journey in Nigeria: Opportunities and challenges. Retrieved from <https://home.kpmg/ng/en/home/insights/2020/09/digital-transformation-journey-in-nigeria.html>
- Kumar, A., & Verma, R. (2020). Effect of digital marketing on consumer purchase behavior in India's e-commerce sector. *Journal of Retailing*, 96(3), 40-50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretai.2020.03.004>
- Kumar, V., & Reinartz, W. (2018). Customer relationship management: Concept, strategy, and tools (3rd ed.). Springer.
- Lemon, K. N., & Verhoef, P. C. (2016). Understanding customer experience throughout the customer journey. *Journal of Marketing*, 80(6), 69-96. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jm.15.0420>
- Lovelock, C., & Patterson, P. (2015). Services marketing (7th ed.). Pearson Australia.
- Nwachukwu, C., & Okoro, A. (2020). Influence of digital literacy on the adoption of e-commerce platforms in Nigeria. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 40, 100949. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elerap.2020.100949>
- Ogunleye, J., & Folarin, K. (2019). Challenges of adopting CRM systems in SMEs in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 14(7), 20-32. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v14n7p20>
- Rahman, H., & Ali, S. (2021). Effect of social media engagement on brand loyalty in the fashion industry in Bangladesh. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*, 25(4), 613-628. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFMM-11-2020-0241>
- Rogers, E. M. (2003). Diffusion of innovations (5th ed.). Free Press.
- Venkatesh, V., & Davis, F. D. (2000). A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: Four longitudinal field studies. *Management Science*, 46(2), 186-204. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.46.2.186.11926>
- Verhoef, P. C., Broekhuizen, T., Bart, Y., Bhattacharya, A., Dong, J. Q., Fabian, N., & Haenlein, M. (2021). Digital transformation: A multidisciplinary reflection and research agenda. *Journal of Business Research*, 122, 889-901. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.09.022>

- Vial, G. (2019). Understanding digital transformation: A review and a research agenda. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 28(2), 118-144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsis.2019.01.003>
- Vial, G. (2019). Understanding digital transformation: A review and a research agenda. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 28(2), 118-144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsis.2019.01.003>
- Vial, G. (2019). Understanding digital transformation: A review and a research agenda. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 28(2), 118-144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsis.2019.01.003>
- Vial, G. (2019). Understanding digital transformation: A review and a research agenda. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 28(2), 118-144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsis.2019.01.003>
- Williams, J., & Taylor, S. (2019). Impact of mobile technology on customer satisfaction in the retail banking sector in the UK. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 24(2), 156-167. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41264-019-00028-5>
- Zeithaml, V. A., Bitner, M. J., & Gremler, D. D. (2018). *Services marketing: Integrating customer focus across the firm* (7th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.